

Effectiveness of Emotional Coaching Technique in The Reduction of Academic Stress Among Undergraduates: The Implications for Counselling

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Abstract

The study investigated specifically the relative effectiveness of emotional coaching technique in the reduction of academic stress among undergraduates in the universities. The design of the study was quasi experimental, two research questions and two null hypotheses were posited for the study. The moderating variables were the interactive effects of gender and self-efficacy. The population of the study comprised of 187 male and female undergraduates drawn from eight (8) colleges in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, who were diagnosed as having academic stress. The undergraduates who participated in the treatment programme were got through posters/ publicities with only 300 level students experiencing academic stress who were screened from 241 students who responded to the invitations/publicities. The two instruments used were general self-efficacy (GSE) and students academic stress scale (SASS). Data collected were analyzed using ANCOVA and scheffe Post-Hoc. The finding of the study include: there was significant main interactive effect of treatment in the reduction of academic stress level of the participants. In recommendation, agricultural science students should be provided with a good environment to be able to cope effectively during the academic stress which they pass through in their studies, and conclusion was made.

Key words: Emotional Coaching, Academic Stress, Technique, Counselling, Undergraduates

Introduction

Academic stress is a time most undergraduate students experience stress in their academics, a period of struggle with studies and also a period of inability to cope with the environment in which they are studying. Previous studies conducted in academic environments have shown that academic stress affects university students, thus it is worthy of notes for lecturers and the university administrators to pay attention to this problems (Busari, 2012).

Stress in academic institution may have positive effect and negative consequences. Further, academic stress is any factor which internally or externally makes adaption to the environment difficult, it reduces increased effort on the part of the individual to maintain a state of equilibrium between self and external environments. It is worthy of notes that undergraduate students should learn and acquire basic developmental skills to improve on economic conditions of their respective nations. Stress is a physical and

mental response to taking challenges in a normal situation but when it becomes excessive it becomes a problem. Such as American Psychologist (2010), Lambert and Ogeles (2004) in Ikpekaogu, et al, (2016) who did research work in academic stress using interpersonal relationship technique in modifying academic stress. All the above researchers found out that the treatment generally reduced the academic stress of the subjects.

According to Busari (2014), many scholars in the field of behavioral sciences have carried out extensive studies on stress and the outcome of it, and concluded that the topic needs more attention. Ikpekaogu, Ekennia and Ajoku (2016) describe academic stress as a force which affects human beings physically, mentally, emotionally, psychologically, socially and spiritually. While some researchers describe academic stress as wear and tear stressors cause on the human body, including the distribution of mental and behavioral patterns (Busari, 2011). Nadamuri and Ch, (2011) described it as significant source of symptomatic stress.

Students with strong sense of personal competence approach difficult tasks as challenges to be mastered rather than as threats to be avoided (Deb, Strode & Sun, 2015). Academic stress affect each student in varying ways and all individuals regardless of their developmental stage (Banerjee & Charterjee, 2016). It is important to note that individual stress signals fall into four categories namely thoughts, feelings, behaviours and physical symptoms, when under stress one may experience any of these symptoms. Too much academic stress may seriously affect students' physical and psychological state which may diminish self-esteem, create a cycle of self-blame and lusts (Texas, 2013). Therefore, the experience of academic stress and other forms of it are more often compounding and have devastating negative effects on the academic and intellectual wellbeing of undergraduate students. This has been causing serious damage to students' future aspirations, self-concept, self-efficacy, self-esteem and makes them behave and develop mood deregulation, inferiority complex, deviant behavior and sometimes isolate from others due to incompetency.

Some researchers have done research works using survey studies on academic stress while others used varying techniques. This writer used emotional coaching technique (ECT) technique and quasi experimental studies in assisting undergraduates to cope during academic stress. Emotional coaching (EC) developed by Hromek (2007) refers specifically to skills development around emotional issues. Coaching is a future oriented, transformations process where a coach and a young person work together to reach important goals for their wellbeing, coaching is neither counselling nor discipline. It is a structured relationship that encourages young people to take action and to develop competence in social and emotional skills in a self and supportive environment, emotional coaching should be part of wider treatment package, echo-systemic that involves families, schools, social networks and when necessary, medical and therapeutic agencies.

Natural coaching relationship occurs within schools families and communities and offer certain self-guards around support for the coach and student. That is, to see the young person's strengths and understand their background, and to sustain their long term ties. The more natural coaching relationship exists between young people and teachers, counsellors and psychologists, little training may be needed in other to use the programme presented for emotional controls. Emotional coaching is tricky and any perceived threat is met with furious, while sometimes physical defense is taken to heart and added to a store of negative self-concept. It is interesting to note that University students are young undergraduates who need a supportive team of people that understand the nature of their emotional difficulties and are willing to maintain relationship with them. This team includes parents, teachers, coaches, counsellors, social workers and when necessary, psychologists and child psychiatrists.

Coaching provides a chance to invent new and promising futures with young people through goal setting and skills development. Emotional coaching focuses on deciphering and managing emotions in oneself and others, coaches are able to mediate between young people's emotional crisis in a way that

empowers them to take responsibility for their relations and increase self-regulation (Roffey, 2016). According to (Smith, 2012) transformation in gender roles and social norms undertake different strategies to reduce academic stress. The persistence gender inequality, poverty and hunger call, for a modification in the manner students react to academic stress. For this research study, the interactive and moderating variables gender and self-efficacy are examined. University students perceive and experience specific stress effects in their various studies, they also foster the development of varying kinds of methods as regards the management of different stressful conditions.

Self-efficacy is defined as a self-evaluation of one's competence to successfully execute a course of action necessary to reach desired outcome (Ikpekaogu, et al, 2016). For this reason, there are some factors that are capable of affecting students' academic examinations, their general results or their external examinations. These factors are irregular class attendance, excessive work load, too much sleep, lack of good nutrition or poor feeding and lack of exercise, with physical inactivity, poor eating and sleeping patterns (Bennet & Holloway, 2014). Awoyemi in Ikpekaogu et al, (2016) contend that self-efficacy seems to be especially promising as a guide for changing negative attitude, as it offers the counsellor a set of specific strategies for accessing low expectation and for treating them.

Students need not to give up easily in challenges ahead, falling quickly to anxiety and depression when faced with difficult tasks, or rather dwell in their individual weakness and on all kinds of negative outcomes instead of concentrating on how to achieve success (Adeyemo & Ogunyemi, 2012). They maintained that this is evidence that some researchers have made efforts to relate self-efficacy with academic performance. Many researchers have carried out studies that revealed that self-efficacy improves achievement outcomes in examinations and Ramirez and Beilock, (2011). This means that students should be motivated based on their behaviors, efforts and persistence including as they believe that they are capable of doing well if motivated. (Banerjee & Charterjee, 2016). This research work investigated the effectiveness of Emotional Coaching Technique (ECT) in the reduction of academic stress among undergraduates in Southern Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Academic stress among university undergraduates is a huge concern and source of worry to researchers, curriculum planners, counsellors, psychologists, educationists, teachers, social workers, parents, students and other education authorities. Academic stress has been viewed as challenging to students in different ways by some researchers and counselling psychologists, these areas are low self-esteem, low self-concept, anger, anxiety, poor academic performance, membership of drug abuse, cultism, groups, poor concentration in the class, mental health challenges, absent-mindedness in the class, poor adjustment in the class, absent from class learning, classwork and class activities, regular involvement in examination malpractices and with a disciplinary actions, lack of reading practices at home, abandonment of home work and school assignments among others. Students and adolescents in a school system experience all these huge concerns of academic stress which require proper theories, skills, techniques and professional counsellors, psychologists and creativities that deal with mental, psychological and human developmentalists to see to well-being of the ugly consequences of undergraduate students academic stress (Reddy, Menon & Thattil, 2018; Nnachi 2012 & 2013).

The effect of academic stress is very damaging physically and psychologically and when students cannot manage it, it becomes pathological threats. Academic stress has devastating effects on undergraduate students experiencing the problems such as frustration, financial challenges, conflicts, pressure from parents and their peers, placement related stressors, self-imposed poor preparations (Busari, 2012).

Students with academic stress manifest various behaviors such as awaking with restlessness, inability to relax and easily changing moods as well as over reactions to minor stress. They also engage in

excessive smoking, excessive eating, over sleep, losing memory, resentment and awaking with feeling of anxiety (Ikpekaogu, et al, 2016). Psychologically, they experience some disorders such as abdominal pains, sleep paralysis, tension, headache, toothache, phobia, fear of examinations, sexual problems, mental health psychology, irritable behavior, bowel syndrome, insulin resistance, drug abuse, dissociative-identity-disorder, cluster headaches, bipolar disorders and bullying (Texas, 2013). The researchers observed that some of such students practice reserved psychology disordered behaviours.

The purpose of the study

The purpose of this research study is to find out the effectiveness of emotional coaching technique in the reduction of academic stress level among undergraduates of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Abia State.

The aim of this study is the attempt to send a warning signal to those that hope to be involved in reducing academic stress of students.

Specifically the study determined:

1. The main interactive effect of treatment, in the reduction of academic stress level among undergraduates.
2. The interactive effect of gender and self-efficacy singly on the reduction of academic stress among undergraduates.
3. The interactive effect of gender and self-efficacy combined on the reduction of academic stress among undergraduates.

Significance of the study

This study is expected to bring about a set of positive outcomes for university students including fewer unintended drop outs, less sexual risk taking behaviors, reduction in conflict and frustration, prevention or reduction of substance or alcohol use, less delinquent behavior, better university attendance, improved academic performance and better mental health generally. The study is unique in its use of one psychological therapy Emotional Coaching Therapy (ECT).

The study added to knowledge in the area of educational and counselling psychology, especially in the use of psychotherapy in handling problems noted to be academic stress.

Further, emerging scholars, especially those in the field of psychology, counselling and education could benefit immensely from the study because it is an example of research work that shows systematic approaches of dealing with individual's emotionally inappropriate behavior and society's expectations from university students.

The researcher's output is also of great benefit to educationists, psychologists, counsellors and parents as the findings are also sources of presentation of enlightenment on the relevance of using psychology, counselling and education in handling traumatic experiences. Scientific and systematic approach to the treatment of academic challenges may be attributed to individual's academic poor performance.

This study is also peculiar in the sense that psychological intervention is one major factor that could reduce academic stress, hence the sensitive and awareness of academic programmes made available for parents, guardians, lecturers and educational stakeholders that highly needed to intervene in the handling of academic stress. (Awosusi & Adegboya, 2012)

Research Questions

Two research questions were formulated for the study as follow:

1. What is the effect of treatment level of emotional coaching technique (ECT) in the modification of academic stress among undergraduates?

2. What is the effect of gender and self-efficacy in the modification of academic stress among undergraduates either singly or combined?

Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were posited for this study. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance, and state them as follow:

1. There is no significant main interactive effect of treatment in the reduction of academic stress level among participants
2. There is no significant main interactive effect of gender and self-efficacy either singly or combined in the reduction of academic stress level among participants.

Methods

Research Question One: The results of the study are presented below:

What is the level of main effect of emotional coaching therapy in the reduction of academic stress level among the undergraduate students at post-test? The above research question was analyzed using frequency distribution and percentages for questionnaire item numbers 1-2.

Percentage Analysis of the Emotional Coaching Therapy (ECT) Group

Responses in the Reduction of Academic Stress.

Quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2015) quasi experiment is a subject to experimental random and control groups are not possible.

The study is an experimental research which adopted 3×2 randomized factorial matrix in rows consisted the interactive moderating variables gender and self-efficacy. The study was conducted in Abia State, Nigeria. Abia State is inhabited by both indigene and non-indigene with varying cultural groups. Abia State has two main Universities. The population of the study comprised 1st male and female undergraduates of MOUAAU who were diagnosed of having academic stress. The participants were attracted through posters/publicities in the various colleges as the University runs collegiate system at the auditorium and the participants were down from only 300 level students in the University.

The sample for the study consisted of 103 undergraduate students experiencing academic stress, using the publicity. The 741 students who responded to the publicity experiencing academic stress using the publicity volunteered to be screened to determine their level of academic stress scale.

The 187 subjects who scored 50 and above were regarded as a result was classified as the population of this study. On the other hand, subjects who scored below 50 were excluded from the study. From the population, 103 were sampled into three groups using simple random technique. The 103 students were further screened, as self-efficacy and gender.

Jerusalemites, two instruments were used for the study. Namely: General self-efficacy. Schwartzer and students. Academic stress scale (SASS) (Bursari, 2012).

The two instruments were used to elicit information on the respondent's level of Academic stress according to their sections.

Three experts from psychology, Guidance/Counselling and Measurement and Evaluation determined the scale and self-efficacy face and content validity. The experts ensured their blue prints were followed including checking and eliminating ambiguities. The SASS correlated positively with related test at 0.77 and negatively with unrelated instrument at 0.83. Test re-test method was used to determine the reliability of the SASS and GSE to 10 subjects in the University demonstration school within the target population not included in the study. The criterium for accepting or rejecting the hypotheses was based on when the calculated value was higher than the critical value and vice-versa.

S/N	Emotional Coaching Therapy (ECT) (Test of Academic Stress)	Yes	No	Percentages (%) Yes	Percentages (%) No	Remarks
1.	Do you sometimes evaluate yourself performing below expectation in academic due to stress.	8	2	80%	20%	100
2.	You do not find time to relax, rest or stop worries after stressful learning?	8	2	80%	20%	100
3.	You use drugs like alcohol, cocaine, marijuana etc. in other to relax when you have academic stress?	7	3	70%	30%	100
4.	Are you aware that your low CGPA is affecting your entire life style?	7	3	70%	30%	100
5.	You thought being stressed helps students to learn fast	8	2	80%	20%	100
6.	Does academic stress make you want to engage in antisocial behavior like poor relationship and low academic performance?	8	2	80%	20%	100
7.	Does academic stress create difficulty for you in coping with your life challenge?	7	3	70%	30%	100
8.	Do you have problem of listening, reading and understanding anything anytime you are stressed?	7	3	70%	30%	100
9.	Does your failure affect you, your parents, guardians, teachers and elders?	8	2	80%	20%	100
10.	Do you feel you may not do well in life if you continue to miss classes?	7	3	70%	30%	100
	Aggregate percentages	75	25			

The table above showed that the behavioral indicators of most of the subjects were clearly manifested between 20% to 80% prevalence before the treatment therapy.

The table also presented the results obtained in the study. This was based on the analysis of the two hypotheses posited for the study.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant main interactive effect of treatment in the reduction of academic stress level among the participants.

To test this hypothesis, ANCOVA was adopted to analyse the post-test scores of the participants in their academic stress using the pre-test scores as covariate to ascertain if the post experimental differences are statistically significant and the summary of the analysis is presented below.

Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) Post-Test

Treatment in the Reduction of Academic Stress among the Participants

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta
Corrected Model	779555.143 ^a	18	43308.619	31.175	.000	.870
Intercept	74471.122	1	74471.122	53.606	.000	.390
Pre-score	48165.132	1	48165.132	34.670	.000	.292
Control group * group	415786.003	2	207893.001	149.646	.000	.781
Gender	594.911	1	594.911	.428	.515	.005
Self-efficacy	66.013	2	33.006	.024	.977	.001
Control group *gender	4298.572	2	2149.286	1.547	.219	.036
Control group *self-efficacy	8880.524	4	2220.131	1.598	.182	.071
Gender *self-efficacy	3165.150	2	1582.575	1.139	.325	.026
Self-efficacy						
Error	116695.265	84	1389.229			
Total	4702464.000	99				
Corrected Total	896250.408	98				

- a. R Squared = .870 (Adjusted R Squared = .842). The result from the table above showed that there is significant main interactive effect of treatment in the reduction of academic stress of the participants ($F_2, \eta^2 = 149.646, p < 0.05, r^2 = 0.781$). This means there is significant difference in the mean score of the level of academic stress of the undergraduates exposed to ECT when compared with the control group. Hence, hypothesis one is rejected. It was therefore concluded that there is significant main interactive effect of treatment in the reduction of academic stress of participants. This implies that Emotional Coaching Technique (ECT) is effective in reducing academic stress of participants.

To further provide information in the reduction of the severity of the participants among the two groups (ECT and control), the researcher ascertained the direction of the reference and determined the magnitude of the mean scores of the participants in the treatment and the control group. Thus, the Scheffe Post-Hoc analysis was calculated and presented below.

Scheffe Post-Hoc Analysis showing significant Differences in the Treatment Group

Treatment group	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Emotional Coaching Therapy	44	120.91	
Control group	31		311.10
Sig		1.000	1.000

There is significant difference in the post-hoc test mean scores in the level of reduction of the academic stress of the undergraduates exposed to ECT and control group. The participants in ECT (mean = 120.91) reduced the academic stress significantly better than those in the control group (mean = 311.10). In achieving all these, the researcher employed quasi experimental design for the study.

Conclusion

This study was designed to study the effectiveness of emotional coaching technique in the reduction of academic stress among undergraduates in South-Eastern and Western Nigeria. Gender and self-efficacy were the interactive effects moderating variables. To this effect, the selected participants screened had to undergo some training. The required data was collected and analyzed revealing the outcome of the study. Based on the findings, the following conclusions were reached:

- Treatment, gender and self-efficacy, had significant interactive effect in the reduction of academic stress level of the agricultural science students in the university, as gender relates to masculine and feminine Nnachi, (2011).

Counselling Implications of the findings

The findings of this study clearly showed that emotional coaching technique was effective in the reduction of academic stress of agricultural science students in the university. This finding has implication for the university students, teachers, school counsellors, curriculum planners and other researchers who may find out other gaps to carry out further studies with the technique.

Due to stress associated with this course in the university, agricultural science students are destabilized mentally, physically and psychologically which often prevents the undergraduates from focusing completely on their studies which results in failure, low cumulative grade point average (CGPA) and most times are withdrawn from the university. Several studies have proven that emotional coaching is capable of helping these agricultural science students and university students to reduce their academic stress using other techniques. Students whose actions in drug use and misuse due to academic stress are meant to show relapse behavior based on the strategies used for their reduction, this is in line with implication stated by Des, Strodi & Sun (2015).

Further implication of the study is that, it provides the basic information necessary for identifying causes of academic stress of the undergraduates to teachers, counsellor and educational psychologists and also equip practitioners as regards the knowledge of conceptualizing students' challenges and adequately manage the menace using emotional coaching technique.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant main interactive, effect of gender and self-efficacy in the reduction of academic stress among participants.

The results from above showed there is no significant main interactive effect of gender and self-efficacy either singly or combined in reduction of academic stress of participants thus: ($F_{4, 78} = 1.139$, $p > 0.05$, $\eta^2 = 0.026$). This means there is no significant interactive effect of, gender and self-efficacy in the reduction of the academic stress of participants. Hence, hypothesis two is accepted.

Summary of findings:

This study examined the effectiveness of Emotional Coaching Technique in the reduction of academic stress level among agricultural science undergraduate students which were generalized to three Federal Universities of Agriculture in Nigeria. The findings of the study are summarized as follow;

1. There was significant interactive effect of treatment in the reduction of academic stress level of participants.
2. There was no significant interactive effect of, gender and self-efficacy in the reduction of academic stress of participants.

These findings revealed the outcome of the study.

The study outlined the prevalence and causes of academic stress and how these factors could affect undergraduates' studies in all the universities. The approach used in this study makes it unique. The inherited trainings of undergraduates has various challenges, processes and causes that are discussed in this study which critically showed that this may have adverse effect on their academics though their ideas may not always be negative, as the researcher deliberately took a close look at the negative part that have been generated.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were drawn from the findings of the study. The emotional coaching technique was effective in reducing academic stress of undergraduates in the university. It is therefore recommended that conscious efforts be made by counselling psychologists, educationist and other related professionals to adopt the technique when handling academic stress issues with its associated challenges, taking into cognizance the academic vigour and encourage undergraduates to study effectively. The researcher believes that if the students could be coping during academic stress, counsellors should choose to speak beyond the classroom environment, speak to the public as it was done in the course of this study, and take advantage of media houses to amplify their findings. Educational psychologists should organize academic seminars outside campus and other programmes so as to sensitize undergraduates on how the study could be concurrently adopted to conduct research studies in other challenging issues. The effectiveness of emotional coaching technique in reducing academic stress of agricultural science students and counseling interactions could equip the students better to effectively manage challenges they could face during each session. Government could use their findings to plan different programmes and fund the university, provide a good environment to enable students adapt easily to the academic stress which they are passing through.

Parents and guardians of students who have challenges in academic stress could personally undergo such trainings so as to reduce their academic stress. Parents should also be well informed on the need to reduce reaction to stressors that may trigger the academic stress if their wards in the university return home from school. Students should not be directly involved in the challenges faced at home such as financial incapability of parents because they are faced with academic vigours that could affect them in school.

Counseling centres and youth friendly centres and departments should be built in the various universities, it would be of assistance to all the undergraduates to improve their communication skills for healthy interactions.

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